
EFFECT OF AUDIT INDEPENDENCE ON AUDIT QUALITY: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIAN AGRICULTURAL FIRMS

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Abstract

The study determined effect of audit independence on audit quality in Nigerian agricultural firms, using audit committee independence and audit tenure as independent variables, while audit firm reputation represent dependent variable of Nigerian agricultural firms. Ex post facto research design and content analysis were employed by the study. Data were extracted from annual reports and accounts of the sampled agricultural firms. The study employed multiple regression analysis to test the hypotheses. Based on the results, the study found that audit committee independence has a positive and insignificant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria. Also, the study upholds that audit tenure has a negative significant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended, among others, that firms need to ensure that every audited report must be reviewed by the audit committees to confirm that the procedure for auditing complies fully with all applicable laws and guidelines regarding planning and presenting of the financial statement is adhered to.

Keywords: Audit independence, Audit committee independence, Audit tenure and Audit firm reputation

Introduction

The latest failure of foremost businesses because of fraud and doubtful financial reporting practices has highlighted the vital significance of credible, monetary reporting (Slyvia, 2021 in Yeng, & Oppong, 2024). They have also tested the importance of considering the role of auditing inside the broader context of monetary quality. Monetary facts is needed not handiest to evaluate the economic and operational overall performance of the entity within the use of monetary assets but also to serve the records desires of relevant stakeholders on their resources and obligations (Herath & Albarqui, 2017) Auditing performs a critical position in economic great (Ibrahim & Ali,2018). External auditing of economic statements helps serve the wishes of numerous stakeholders through presenting affordable guarantee that the economic statements are unfastened from cloth misstatements (Alwardat, 2019). Velte and Loy (2018) posit that, so that it will ensure financial nice, the auditor's independence is paramount. Jenkins and Stanly (2019) concluded within the same vein that audit independence is foundational to audit exercise (Yeng & Oppong, 2024).

Independence is a major concern in the auditing profession. Corporate scandals like Enron failure confirmed the importance of credulity of audits. Audit independence refers to the ability of the external auditor to act with integrity and impartiality during his/her auditing functions (Akpom & Dimkpah, 2013). Recent challenges of the audit independence assumption have impelled the accounting profession to consider ways of improving the credibility of audit reports (Shockley, 1981). As a result, the accounting profession has considered new ways to improve the credibility of audits. It is constantly facing pressure from the media, stakeholders and investors to minimize (Siryama & Tori, 2018).

Auditor independence increases “the effectiveness of the audit with the aid of making sure that the auditor plans and consists of out the audit objectively” (Chepkorir, 2013). Researchers argue auditing has three specific functions: reveal the actions of managers enhance the facts environment and provide a source of coverage against corporate disasters (Fernando & Randal, 2010). Corporate failures including Enron and WorldCom contributed to the impairment of auditor independence. It is miles believed that when auditors fail to file or identify incorrect information on monetary statements, it may mission the fee of the audit and probably harm the reputation of the company (Fearnley, Beattie & Brandt, 2005).

During main accounting scandals, auditors acquired complaint for increasing their non-audit services. in the course of the Enron and other accounting scandals, in which auditors have been often suspected of complicity, auditors and customers were criticized for, among different matters, sizeable will increase in non-audit offerings (NAS), which include tax offerings supplied through outside auditors (Lassila, 2010).

In the aftermath of a downward economy, the general public's problem for auditor independence became heightened as organizations desired to make certain a business enterprise's adherence to professional accounting requirements and standards (Austin & Herath, 2014). Revised regulations were published via the Securities trade and commission to cope with the occasions for non-audit offerings. Audit companies ought to now create separate classes that divulge all of the fees that have been paid to the firm so that traders are aware of the sorts of prices (Gul, Jaggi & Krishnan 2007). Studies evidence suggests that higher excellent earnings are associated with longer audit tenure than shorter audit tenure. in addition, studies shows that auditors and purchaser firms have a stronger economic bound once auditors had been employed for an extended period of time which leads to personal connections and familiarity. Gul et al, (2007) finish that non-audit prices are likely to affect

auditor independence for companies with shorter auditor tenure, however no longer for companies with longer audit tenure.

Audit quality depends on auditor's independence as proposed by Aren, Randal, Beasley (2014) that the value of auditing depends heavily on the public's perception of the independence of auditors. The same thing was also expressed by Enofe, Nbgame and Ediae (2013) based on the results of research that as auditor's independence increases, the quality of the audit also increases..

Many studies have also been carried out on auditor independence and audit quality. Some of these studies like; Muhammed, Abdulyakeen, Ajide and Oyaleke (2024) examined the effects of audit committees' attributes on the quality of financial reporting of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Yeng and Oppong (2024) ascertained the effects of audit independence on financial reporting quality in the Sub-Sahara African Stock Markets. Sylvia (2021); Babatolu, Aigienohuwa and Uniamikogbo (2016); Amahalu and Ezechukwu (2017) studied the effect of auditor independence on audit quality of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria studied the effect of audit independence on financial reporting quality of listed money banks in Nigeria

There is a dearth study on agricultural firms in Nigeria; as such their studies ended in 2022. This created sectorial and periodic gaps which this study set to fill. It is against the above backdrop that the current study extends previous studies by presenting new evidence about the effect of audit independence on audit quality in Nigerian agricultural firms. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the followings;

1. To evaluate the degree of effect type of audit committee independent has on audit quality of Nigerian agricultural firms.
2. To determine the extent to which audit tenure affect audit quality of Nigerian agricultural firms.

Review of Related Literature

Audit independence

Auditor independence may be defined as an auditor's unbiased mental mindset in making choices at some stage in the audit and financial reporting system. The predominant threats to auditor independence are the prices perceived by using the auditor for audit and non-audit offerings and the duration of the auditor – consumer courting. The impaired independence of an auditor result in terrible audit exceptional and permits for greater income control and decrease profits first-class (Okolie, 2014).

Internal auditors are liable for preserving their independence below any circumstances in order that evaluations, conclusions, considerations, and hints from the consequences of the audit completed are unbiased and are seen as impartial to any party. Accountant independence as professional behavior impacts the high-quality of the audit opinion given by the accountant (Yeni & Helmayunita 2016). Auditor independence may be impaired with the aid of auditor tenure. because the auditor patron courting lengthens, the auditor might also develop close courting with the consumer and become much more likely to act in favour of control, resulting in reduced objectivity and audit great (Babatolu, Aigienohuwa & Uniamikogbo, 2016).

Meanwhile, the Independent Standards Board (ISB) established a framework for Auditor Independence due to the lack of inconsistent rules and regulations. The framework contains various principles and concepts to help assist the board with writing the standards. This

framework defines auditor independence as “freedom from the factors that compromise, or can reasonably be expected to compromise, an auditor’s ability to make unbiased audit decisions” (McGrath, 2001). Standards are based on a model that involves three key steps: identify threats to the auditor’s independence and analyze their significance, evaluate the effectiveness of potential safeguards and determine an acceptable level of independence risk. Researchers reported that the definition of independence does not require the auditor to be completely free of all the factors that affect the ability to make an unbiased audit decision, but only free from those that rise to the level of compromising that ability” (McGrath, 2001). The overall goal with independence is to ensure financial reports are reliable and improve capital markets efficiency. Independence is an essential attribute for audits because it determines how credible and reliable financial statements will be to investors. Independence has been the focus of almost constant controversy, debate and analysis (Law, 2008).

Audit committee

An audit committee represents a single of the several managerial oversight tools. corporate governance lapses in Nigeria, like the ones at Skye bank % and Diamond bank %, wherein managers are openly violating the CAMA Act (2004) by means of presenting illicit advances to personalities and their pals, gift an obstacle to the audit committee. It calls for all publicly traded companies to shape an audit committee, which have to include three self-sufficient administrators and at the very least three representatives of the stockholders, with at the least one of their participants having experience in finance or accounting (Salloum, et al. 2014). The audited record must additionally be reviewed by way of the audit committee to verify that the technique for auditing complies completely with all relevant legal guidelines and guidelines concerning making plans and imparting of the financial announcement. It equally displays that the impartial auditor has very well reviewed every pertinent report and the relevant requirements. As a end result, audit committee has a more possibility to restriction the proposal of the usage of discretionary accruals to reap smooth effects. in addition to making certain extraordinary requirements for monetary public disclosure, the committee is also in fee of preserving track of accounting strategies, upholding the autonomy of auditors, and controlling adherence to guard the objectives of stockholders. This boosts the public's and shareholders' hopes for improved enterprise transparency (Jerry & Saidu 2017).

Audit Committee Independent refers to the degree of autonomy and objectivity that the audit committee possesses in carrying out its responsibilities within an organization. The primary role of the audit committee is to oversee the financial reporting process, monitor the internal control systems, and supervise the internal and external audit functions (Kantudu & Samaila, 2015). To effectively fulfill these duties, the audit committee must maintain a level of independence from the management and other stakeholders who may have vested interests. By maintaining independence, the audit committee can provide a critical check and balance within the organization, enhancing the credibility and reliability of the financial reporting process and promoting effective corporate governance practices (Adegboye, *et al.* 2020).

Audit tenure

An audit firm’s tenure may be defined as the period of time an auditor plays services for a client. Risk related to the lack of independence is improved once consumer relationships are maintained for a protracted time frame. However, different people consider having an enduring and faithful courting will augment independence. As an instance, “lengthy tenure is beneficial as auditors benefit know-how in the discipline that they audit and may lessen the auditor’s capacity to detect irregularities or material misstatements” (UKEssays). Shockley (1981) defined how “complacency, loss of innovation, much less rigorous audit processes and

a found out confidence within the client might also get up after long association with the consumer.” A advice to rotate auditors became suggested through the Metclaf subcommittee to keep away from this difficulty. Educational studies has validated that there are extra unsuccessful audits within the beginning of auditor-patron relationships further to decrease income with audits which have shorter time frames. Apparently, buyers praise long auditor-consumer relationships with decrease price of debt (Mansi, Maxwell, & Miller, 2004).

Audit Quality

Preceding literature the dimensions of the auditor may be considered as subrogate of the audit pleasant (Carcello & Nagy, 2004). Audit satisfactory defined as auditors use some technics to apprehend misstatements in customers accounting device and document the misstatements. Audit best is the arguable troubles for the recent many years and most previous evidence shows that loss of audit exceptional is a number of the maximum critical reason for monetary and company scandals (Soltani, 2014).

The most definition of audit fine, which has been widely well-known by way of pupils, is the one by means of DeAngelo (1981) which states that the first-class of audit offerings is described to be the marketplace-assessed joint chance that a given auditor will both find out a breach within the client’s accounting gadget and document the breach. This definition widely method that audit first-rate depends on the opportunity that the auditor discovers a misstatement in a monetary announcement and actually reviews the misstatement. If auditors aren't unbiased, they may be less probable to report misstatements, which negatively impacts audit first-class. As an end result, it could be argued that the lower the diploma of independence of the auditor, the lower the quality of audit services may be. Being an important implication of her definition, she adds that audit failure, being a financial statement with omissions and/or misstatements, is less likely to occur when audit services are of higher quality. High quality auditors with a substantial reputation for detecting and reporting irregularities have great incentives to reduce the likelihood of audit failure in order to retain their reputation. In a situation of a litigation of an auditor, auditors therefore often try to settle the matter out of court in order to avoid damage to their reputation. She argues that audit quality is inversely related to, although seldom seen, litigation against an auditor. Thus, when using the litigation rate as a measure for audit quality, auditors with relatively low litigation rates provide a higher quality of audit services (Palmrose, 2001). Francis (2004) describes audit quality as a theoretical continuum ranging from very low to very high audit quality. In addition to the definition, he argues that audit failures occur on the lower end of the quality continuum.

Empirical Review

Muhammed, Abdulyakeen, Ajide and Oyaleke (2024) examined the results of audit committees’ attributes on the pleasant of financial reporting of listed client items corporations in Nigeria. The information for the look at changed into obtained from the yearly reports of the pattern of sixteen purchaser goods corporations listed for the duration 2009 to 2022. The information become analyzed the usage of fixed effect regression evaluation after undertaking the Hausman check and the Breusch-Pagan take a look at. The take a look at observed that audit committees independence (ACI), audit committees’ size (ACS), and shareholders involvement within the committees (SIAC) have a huge tendency to enhance the same old of published monetary facts of Nigerian purchaser items businesses which are listed.

Yeng and Oppong (2024) ascertained the effects of audit independence on economic reporting great inside the Sub-Sahara African stock Markets. Their records had been

generated from the annual monetary reviews of 106 listed companies in the 6 sub-Saharan African inventory markets of ten- year length from 2012 to 2021. The examine observed that audit tenure has a effective effect and is widespread in explaining economic reporting quality. The results further display that audit company size has a effective effect but is insignificant in explaining financial reporting great. Audit expenses had been discovered to have a effective and huge effect on financial reporting.

Priyanti and Dewi (2019) determined the effect of audit tenure, audit firm size and client's company size on financial reporting quality of comprised public firms listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2012 to 2017. The multiple linear regressions and the analysis showed that audit tenure and public accounting firm size do not have effect on financial reporting quality. The study did not find any significant relationship between audit tenure and financial quality.

Kariuki and Oluoch (2020) ascertained the relationship between audit size and financial reporting quality of listed firms on the Nairobi Stock Exchange. Data was derived from the financial statements for period 2010- 2019. It was found that there was a positive effect of audit size on financial reporting quality at the Nairobi Stock Exchange. Also, there was a positive relationship between audit committee independence and financial reporting quality. Oyedokum (2020) determined that listed companies dealing in purchaser goods in Nigeria have a substantial high quality courting among audit company length and monetary reporting first-class. It was endorsed that listed patron items pay particular attention to the kind of Audit Company that they engage to audit their financial statements with the intention to in flip give a boost to their monetary reporting best.

May and Rasha (2019) examined the effect of audit quality on firm performance. It uses financial statements of non-financial firms listed as EGX 100. The population studied consists of thirty non-financial firms. The study covers a five year period 2010-2014. It applies panel data analysis. Independent Variables are Auditor Experience (measured by Big-4) and Auditor Independence (measured by auditor Rotation ROT). Dependent Variables are Return on Assets ROA and Return on Equity ROE. In accordance with the Random Effect Model results, BIG 4 and ROT have an insignificant impact on the ROA and ROE of the firm. External and internal financial statement users may benefit from the study only when dealing with high-profit firms. Ezejiofor and Erhirhie (2018) investigated the effect of audit quality on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study adopted ex post facto research design, data for the study were collected from annual reports and accounts of quoted Nigerian deposit money banks. Regression analysis and coefficient correlation were employed to test the formulated hypotheses. Findings revealed that there is a significant effect between audit quality and financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks. Amahalu and Ezechukwu (2017) ascertained the determinants of audit quality with a focus on decided on Deposit money Banks listed at the ground of Nigeria inventory alternate from 2010-2015. The applicable facts were subjected to statistical analysis the usage of Pearson coefficient of correlation, regular Least square (OLS) and Granger causality take a look at with the aid of E-view nine.0. The result of this examine found out that there may be a advantageous and statistically enormous dating between audit charges, audit tenure, audit company length and audit satisfactory. It turned into also empirically established that audit fees, audit tenure, audit company length have a statistically giant courting with audit satisfactory of banks indexed on the floor of Nigerian inventory change at five% stage of importance. Zayol and Kukeng (2017) reviewed literature related to auditor independence and audit quality in order to determine the effect of the former on the latter. The ex post facto research design is employed. Information for this study was obtained from secondary sources

to include journals, text books and other internet materials. Based on the review, findings show that there is a strong relationship between auditor independence and audit quality. The review also revealed four threats to auditor independence, which are client importance, non-audit services (NAS), audit tenure, and client's affiliation with CPA firms.

Amahalu and Ezechukwu (2017) ascertained the determinants of audit quality with a focus on selected Deposit Money Banks listed on the floor of Nigeria Stock Exchange from 2010-2015. Using audit fees, audit tenure, audit firm size and audit quality Pearson coefficient of correlation, Ordinary Least Square OLS) and Granger causality test with the aid of (E-view 9.0. The result of this study revealed that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between audit fees, audit tenure, audit firm size and audit quality. Babatolu, Aigienohuwa and Uniamikogbo (2016) examined the effect of auditor independence on audit quality of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select sample size of seven (7) listed deposit money banks from a population of twenty (20). Secondary data were sourced from the audited annual report of the sampled banks. Descriptive statistics, correlation and ordinary least square (OLS) regression were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between audit fee, audit firm rotation and audit quality. There exists negative relationship between audit firm tenure and audit quality. The correlation between audit quality and leverage was strong, negative and statistically significant. The correlation between audit quality and company size was strong, positive and statistically significant.

Bishnu and Ranjan (2016) examined the determining factors of the audit committee independence in the financial sector of Bangladesh by employing a cross-sectional regression analysis on 72 financial firms. The study revealed that firms with large boards and more non-executive directors tend to provide more independence to the auditors. Also, large firms with potential growth opportunities show less interest in giving freedom to the audit committee members; whereas firms with the higher leverage demand more audit committee independence to confirm quality monitoring and quality financial statements. The study, however, reveals a negative relationship between the size of the audit committee and its work independence. The study also does not find any significant association between audit committee independence and presence of experts in the audit committee, percentage of insider ownership, free cash flow, and firms' profitability.

Bogale (2016) investigated the determinants of external audit quality proxied by discretionary (abnormal) accrual based on audit firm. The study adopted quantitative method of research approaches to test a series of research hypothesis. Consequently, the study selected a sample of eighteen (18) companies for the period of five years (2011-2015) in Ethiopian manufacturing share companies. The results of panel least square regression analysis show that certified audit professionals' and joint provision of audit and non-audit services have statistically significant and positive relationship with manufacturing share companies' external audit quality.

Mahmoud (2015) decided the effect of joint audit on audit high-quality: Empirical proof from groups indexed on the Egyptian inventory exchange. A sample of 32 corporations indexed on the Egyptian inventory exchange in the duration 2009 via 2013 representing a hundred and sixty firm- year observations become determined. A couple of regression model turned into used to investigate the information. The study layout did no longer expose the complete populace wherein a sample of thirty became taken. Findings showed that agencies audited by joint auditors are greater conservative than agencies audited by means of unmarried auditors. Causholli, Chambers and Payne (2015) investigated the impact of promoting non-audit

services on auditor independence in the United States. The study did not expose the have a look at layout employed as well as the studied population and sample length. Findings obtained from statistical regressions of bizarre accruals located sturdy proof that the anticipated destiny provision of non-audit offerings does represent a source of impaired independence in the cutting-edge 12 months.

Methodology

Ex-post facto research design and content analysis were adopted for the study. This is appropriate because the study aims at measuring the relationship between one variable and another, in which the variables involved are not manipulated by the researcher.

This study population of the study consists of five Agricultural firms in Nigeria. The data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled agricultural firms in Nigerian Exchange Group from 2013 to 2023. The data for the study were collected from annual reports and accounts of the firms. The independent variables were proxied audit tenure and audit committee independent.

Audit Committee Independence (ACI) = proxy using the proportion of non-directors on the board. Audit tenure involved the length of auditor-client relationship, ‘1’ if 3 years + and ‘0’ if otherwise. Audit quality was represented by audit firm reputation (AFR), set equal to one (1) if the information obtained from banks audited reports show that it is audited by one of the “big 4” audit firms (Price-water house coopers; Akintola Williams Deloitte; KPMG Professional service and Ernst and Young, otherwise zero (0). However, firm leverage was used as the control variable.

Model Specification

This study modified the model of Yeng and Oppong (2024). The model shows that the dependent variable, financial reporting quality can be affected by a set of independent variables. Financial reporting quality is measured by discretionary accruals, while audit independence is measured as proxies of audit firm size, auditor tenure and audit fees.

The regression equation below shows the functional relationship between the variables:

$$DACC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AuDT_{it} + \beta_2 AuDFS_{it} + \beta_3 AuDF_{it} + \beta_4 FS_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \beta_6 ROA_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

When the dependent and independent variables are incorporated into the equation, the study provides the model as shown below:

- $DACC_{it} = FRQ_{it}$ = Financial Reporting Quality
- AuDT = Audit Tenure
- AuDFS = Audit firm size
- ADF = Audit Fees
- FSIZ = Firm Size
- LEV = Leverage
- ROA = Return on Assets
- ε = Error term

The modified model of logistic regression for this study takes the form:

$$ADQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACI_{it} + \beta_2 ADT_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots i$$

Where:

- ADQ_{it} = audit quality, proxied by audit firm reputation (AFR) for firm i in period t.
- ACI_{it} = Audit committee independence for firm i in period t.

ADT_{it} = Audit tenure for firm i in period t .
 LEV_{it} = Firm Leverage for firm i in period t .
 $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = coefficients of the independent variables
 ε = Error term

Method of Data Analysis

The data were analysed relatively via both descriptive and inferential analyses. The descriptive statistics was first conducted in order to gain understanding of the sample characteristics as regards the selected variables. Inferential statistical analysis was carried out with multiple regression analysis via of E-Views 9.0 statistical software.

Decision Rule

At a significance level of 5%, the statistical significance of the analysis was evaluated using P-values (with an alpha of 0.05). When the P-value is lower than 5%, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, if the P-value is equal to or greater than 5%, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Analysis of Data

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	ADQ	ACI	ADT	LEV
Mean	0.545455	3.909091	0.454545	0.407630
Median	1.000000	4.000000	0.000000	0.559998
Maximum	1.000000	5.000000	1.000000	0.582724
Minimum	0.000000	2.000000	0.000000	0.150181
Std. Dev.	0.502519	0.908249	0.502519	0.183057
Skewness	-0.182574	-0.568984	0.182574	-0.312560
Kurtosis	1.033333	2.619117	1.033333	1.258728
Jarque-Bera	9.169213	3.300097	9.169213	7.843929
Probability	0.010208	0.192041	0.010208	0.019802
Sum	30.00000	215.0000	25.00000	22.41963
Sum Sq. Dev.	13.63636	44.54545	13.63636	1.809526
Observations	55	55	55	55

Source: E-View output, 2024

Interpretation of Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive analysis in table 1 above showed that the audit quality (ADQ) of the sampled agricultural firms is 0.545; the maximum of 1.00 with a minimum of 0.000 with a standard deviation of 0.503. The mean value of audit committee independence (ACI) from the sampled observations is 3.909; standard deviation valued at 0.908; a maximum value of 5.000 with a minimum value of 2.000. The mean value of audit tenure (ADT) is 0.454; standard deviation valued at 0.503; a maximum value of 1.000 with a minimum value of 0.000. The mean value of firm leverage (LEV) is 0.407; standard deviation valued at 0.183; a maximum value of 0.583 with a minimum value of 0.150. Skewness is the measure of how much the probability distribution of a random variable departs from the normal distribution. The analysis describes that the probability distribution for ACI (0.192); ADT (0.010) and LEV (0.020) are positively skewed distribution.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 2: Multiple Regression analysis testing the effect between AFR, ACI, ADT and LEV

Dependent Variable: AFR
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 11/04/24 Time: 12:22
 Sample: 2013 2023
 Periods included: 11
 Cross-sections included: 5
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 55

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.248118	0.323861	-0.766124	0.4471
ACI	0.098221	0.067141	1.462905	0.1496
ADT	-0.867363	0.208571	-4.158597	0.0001
LEV	1.972072	0.570215	3.458470	0.0011
R-squared	0.262521	Mean dependent var		0.545455
Adjusted R-squared	0.219139	S.D. dependent var		0.502519
S.E. of regression	0.444057	Akaike info criterion		1.284221
Sum squared resid	10.05654	Schwarz criterion		1.430209
Log likelihood	-31.31609	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.340676
F-statistic	6.051489	Durbin-Watson stat		1.549409
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001320			

Source: E-Views 9.0 Correlation Output, 2024

Interpretation of Regression Result

In Table 2, R-squared and adjusted Squared values were (0.262) and (0.219) respectively. The study showed that the independent variables jointly explain about 22% of the systematic alterations in audit quality of our samples firms over the eleven years periods (2013-2023). The result showed that an adjusted R^2 value of 0.22. The adjusted R^2 , which represents the coefficient of the determinations imply that 22% of the total variation in the dependent variable, audit quality (ADQ) of quoted Agricultural firms in Nigeria is jointly explained by the independent variables; audit committee independence (ACI), audit tenure (ADT) and firm leverage (LEV). The adjusted R^2 of 22% did not constitute a problem to the study because the F- statistics value of 6.051 with an associated $\text{Prob.} > F = 0.001$ showing that the model is fit to explain the effect expressed in the study model and further suggests that the explanatory variables are properly selected, combined and used. The value of adjusted R^2 of 22% also shows that 78% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by other factors not captured in the study model.

Hypothesis One

H_{01} : Audit committee independence does not have a significant effect on audit quality of Nigerian agricultural firms.

The table showed that audit committee independence of firms has a positive and insignificant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.098221 with p value of 0.150 which is not statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.150 higher than 0.05 (5%), this study upholds that audit committee independence has no significant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

HO₁: Audit tenure does not have a significant effect on audit quality of Nigerian agricultural firms.

The table showed that audit tenure of firms has a negative but significant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of -0.867363 with p value of 0.000 which is highly statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%), this study upholds that audit tenure has a significant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The results obtained from the analysis revealed that audit committee independence has no significant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria; also, audit tenure has a significant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria. This result was in line with that of Yeng and Oppong (2024) found that audit tenure has a positive impact and is significant in explaining financial reporting quality. Priyanti and Dewi (2019) showed that audit tenure has effect on financial reporting quality. Kariuki and Oluoch (2020) found that there was a positive relationship between audit committee independence and financial reporting quality. Mutiat Oladuni (2020) May and Rasha (2019) Amahalu and Ezechukwu (2017) empirically verified that audit fees, audit tenure, audit firm size have a statistically significant relationship with audit quality of banks listed on the floor of Nigerian Stock Exchange at 5% level of significance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study determined effect of audit independence on audit quality in Nigerian agricultural firms, using audit committee independence and audit tenure as independent variables, while audit firm reputation represent dependent variable of Nigerian agricultural firms. Data were extracted from annual reports and accounts of the sampled agricultural firms.

Based on the results, the study found that audit committee independence has a positive and insignificant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria. Also, the study upholds that audit tenure has a negative significant effect on audit quality of agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Conclusively, audit independence remains an important element when individuals are conducting an audit. Auditor independence ensures an unbiased perspective and allows financial statements to be more reliable. Firms face the risk of damaging their reputation once auditors fail to report mistakes in their course audits.

Based on the findings, the study recommended the followings:

1. Firms need to ensure that every audited report must be reviewed by the audit committees to confirm that the procedure for auditing complies fully with all applicable laws and guidelines regarding planning and presenting of the financial statement is adhered to.
2. Since, long tenure is beneficial as auditors gain expertise in the field that they audit and this may reduce the auditor's ability to detect irregularities or material misstatements. To avoid learned confidence of auditor in long association with the client, there is need to rotate auditors to avoid this issue.

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